

A Case of Depression *continued from page 30*

week, cardiac status was restored, BP was well maintained at 130/80 and no anginal pains. Lipid profile showed normal level and ECG did not reveal any fresh evidence of active ischaemia. Drug was discontinued on 10.6.1992 and patient continues to remain stable until now.

There was a tremendous improvement in the mental state. Considerable improvement in concentration and work. No more suicidal thoughts. Attitude towards self and others became more positive. Once his employer gave him 40 forms of new issues (shares) to be submitted to the bank. He had to spend 3-4 hours in a queue. He reported that he did not feel dejected when this work was allotted or when he waited in the queue. "It was foolish of me to cry on such occasions". He is happier with his present state. The situation at home is the same,

but he is hopeful of improvement. The relationship with his son has improved and he helps him in organising his work.

During follow up, he would tend to take long time with the Physician. He wouldn't like to go out of the room. He would stay at least 5 minutes by the exit. He would ask small, trivial points and would come back with some query. His questions would be related either to work or family discord and he would try to seek guidance from the physician. It appeared as if he was developing lot of dependence on physician, which later improved. ☒

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Dr. Barvalia practices and teaches at Bombay. He is Asst. Prof. at the Homœopathic College and is a member of the Institute of clinical Research. (ICR). This case is typical of the method of the ICR and shows the open mindedness of Praful to other ideas.

In this case Barvalia, uses the delusion section of the Repertory to pin down the remedy for the exact central feeling of the patient. He uses a rare remedy Hura - which I co-incidentally described earlier as having the feeling "like a leper". This most interesting remedy I have used on the same rubrics and can confirm Barvalia's experience. This case teaches us the necessity of identifying the exact central delusion - also the value of the repertory. Finally the frequent repetition of the dose for several months, as done by Barvalia in this case, should be a matter of thought for us all. (Ed).